

SIMCor

In-Silico testing and validation of Cardiovascular IMplantable devices

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Executive summary

In this deliverable we show the validity of a workflow for creating a Reduced-Order Model (ROM), trained by a limited number of high-fidelity deployment model evaluations to generate input for the fast-to-evaluate deployment model developed in D8.8 Fast-to-evaluate TAVI model based on multi-patch NURBS (TUE). The approximate shape of the deployed TAVI stent can be obtained as output of the fast-to-evaluate model. From this shape, patient-specific information like the paravalvular leakage (PVL) area for a selection of cross-sectional planes across the height of the aorta geometry can be obtained. This workflow can be used as a fast tool for pre-operative risk-assessment of the TAVI procedure. The results can be used to decide whether more accurate high-fidelity simulations are needed for a certain patient, thereby significantly reducing the costs of pre-operative risk assessment.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
ROM	Reduced Order Model
FE(M)	Finite element (method)
TAVI	Transcatheter Aortic Valve Implant
PVL	Paravalvular leakage
SIMCor	In silico testing and validation of cardiovascular implantable devices
GC	Guiding cylinder
(g)PCE	(generalized) Polynomial Chaos Expansion
agPCE	adaptive sparse generalized Polynomial Chaos Expansion
WP	Work package
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Introduction

Patients who suffer from severe aortic stenosis, which is defined by the narrowing of the valve opening caused by stiffening of the leaflets due to calcifications that restrict the valve movement, are often treated by implantation of a prosthetic heart valve. The implantation of the prosthetic valve can be performed surgically. However, for high-risk patients, *transcatheter aortic valve implantation* (TAVI) is a more common and safer option.

The TAVI procedure is a minimally invasive technique in which the prosthetic valve is loaded into a delivery device (catheter) and placed into the aortic root¹. Once the catheter, loaded with the crimped prosthetic valve, is in the correct position, the prosthetic valve is unfolded inside the native aortic valve, thereby pushing the native leaflets out of the way, and restoring the correct flow of blood to the aorta and the systemic arteries. However, several challenges are associated with the TAVI procedure. One of these challenges occurs due to the existence of calcifications on the native leaflets. These calcifications can hinder full deployment of the TAVI stent, resulting in undesirable treatment outcomes, such as excessive *paravalvular leakage* (PVL).

Numerical simulations can be a powerful tool to perform pre-operative risk assessment for undesirable treatment outcomes, tailored to individual patients. Several studies have therefore already focused on reproducing the TAVI procedure in patient-specific geometries (see for example²). However, most studies rely on computationally expensive high-fidelity *finite element method* (FEM) simulations. This computational cost impedes the direct application of such models in the *virtual research environment* (VRE) envisioned in SIMCor. In this VRE, effect simulations are to be performed on large virtual cohorts. This directly leads to the need for a workflow that uses *Reduced-Order Models* (ROM) that can be trained using a limited number of high-fidelity simulations, allowing to perform fast predictions of procedure outcomes.

The aim of this deliverable is to present such a workflow and provide a proof of concept that this workflow can be useful in practice. A limited number of high-fidelity simulations is performed to model device deployment and leaflet deformation. The output of these high-fidelity simulations is used to construct a meta-model, using the *adaptive sparse generalized polynomial chaos expansion* (agPCE). This meta-model can then be used to predict the desired outcome for input parameters for which no high-fidelity simulations are performed. The predicted outcome of the meta-model can be used as input for a fast-to-evaluate deployment model, developed in *D8.8 - Fast-to-evaluate TAVI model based on multi-patch NURBS* (TUE, M28). The approximate shape of the deployed stent can be obtained as output of the fast-to-evaluate model. From this shape, patient-specific information like the PVL area for a selection of cross-sectional planes across the height of the aorta geometry can be obtained. Therefore, this workflow can be used as a tool for fast pre-operative risk-assessment of the TAVI procedure. The workflow is schematically depicted in Figure 1.

¹ Russ C. *et al.*, 2013, Simulation of transcatheter aortic valve implantation under consideration of leaflet calcification, 35th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC).

² Auricchio F. *et al.*, 2014, Simulation of transcatheter aortic valve implantation: a patient-specific finite element approach, Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering.

Figure 1: Explanation of the workflow used throughout this deliverable and how this work connects to other work-packages and deliverables within SIMCor. Figure taken from D8.8 - Fast-to-evaluate TAVI model based on multi-patch NURBS (TUE, M28)

High-fidelity device-deployment model

Theory and boundary conditions for the device-deployment model

The high-fidelity FE model, as presented in *D8.4 - Report on 3D finite element simulation (PHI, M24)*, is used to generate input for the ROM. In this section, the theory of the high-fidelity model will be recapitulated.

The problem described with the high-fidelity model is the deployment of a self-expandable CoreValve TAVI stent inside an aortic geometry. The stent is crimped into the catheter. Inside the catheter, a guiding cylinder is added to keep the outflow part of the CoreValve device from coming into contact with itself. The catheter is positioned inside the aorta geometry, and the catheter covering the crimped device is removed to deploy it within the aortic annulus. A schematic representation of the different parts of the model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the different geometries used to model the deployment of a self-expandable CoreValve stent. Right: Aortic wall. Left: The stent (black) inside the yellow catheter and the guiding cylinder (blue).

The software HyperMesh together with the explicit RADIOSS solver is used to model the deployment. FEM is used to calculate the displacements of each component (*i.e.*, stent, aorta and leaflets) based on the applied forces and boundary conditions. Simplified linear elastic constitutive models for the CoreValve stent and the tissue are used to model the constitutive behavior. The workflow of the numerical model, as it is used for the purpose of this deliverable, is schematically depicted in Figure 3. First, the stent is crimped into the catheter (yellow). A guiding cylinder is added (blue) to prevent the outflow part of the stent from coming into contact with itself. Contact is modeled between the stent and the catheter and the stent and the guiding cylinder. As a next step, the catheter and guiding cylinder are removed, and the stent is deployed. Additional contact is now defined between the stent and the aorta. The aorta geometry is extended at the top and bottom and Dirichlet boundary conditions are applied to fix the nodes of the top and the bottom of the extended parts. This extension is necessary to avoid unrealistic stresses in the region of interest of the simulation.

Figure 3: Schematic workflow of the high-fidelity simulations. From left to right: CoreValve stent crimped inside the catheter, stent is released from the catheter, stent deployed inside aortic geometry.

Input

The high-fidelity simulations are used to generate input for the ROM. The aim of this work is to obtain a characteristic stiffness k_{wall} parameter for the aortic wall, that is used in the fast-to-evaluate model described in D8.8. To this end, three parameters are varied in the linear elastic material models of the aortic wall and the TAVI stent in the high-fidelity model: the Young's modulus of the aorta (E_{wall}), the Young's modulus of the TAVI (E_{TAVI}) and the thickness of the aortic wall (t_{wall}). Characteristic values of these three parameters are obtained from the literature and the sensitivity of these parameters on the aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} is studied. Upper and lower bounds for the three model parameters are chosen and 32 simulations were performed using a quasi-random sample, generated using Sobol sequences. The number of simulations is based on the theory presented in the next section and the outcome of the ROM tool (Q^2 of the constructed meta-model). The input parameters and their upper and lower bounds are presented in Table 1.

Parameter	Literature value	Lower bound	Upper bound
E_{wall} [MPa]	2.0 ³	0.5	5.0
E_{TAVI} [MPa]	51700 ¹	35000	85000
t_{wall} [mm]	2.5 ⁴	0.5	5.0

Table 1: Input parameters to create a quasi-random input sample for the high-fidelity simulations.

Output

In this work, the output of interest of the high-fidelity simulations is a characteristic aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} . The stiffnesses k_{wall} , corresponding to the different parameters of the Sobol set are used to 'train' the ROM. Afterwards, the ROM can be used to obtain a fast prediction of the characteristic aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} , for additional desired values of the input parameters (E_{wall} , E_{TAVI} and t_{wall}). This aortic wall stiffness is subsequently used as input for the fast-to-evaluate model that can perform nearly real-time simulations of the TAVI procedure.

³ Morganti S. *et al.*, 2016, Prediction of patient-specific post-operative outcomes of TAVI procedure: the impact of the positioning strategy on valve performance, Journal of Biomechanics.

⁴ Morganti S. *et al.*, 2014, Simulation of transcatheter aortic valve implantation through patient-specific finite element analysis: two clinical cases, Journal of Biomechanics.

To obtain the stiffness k_{wall} the following approach is used. For every high-fidelity simulation, the contact radial forces and radial displacements in all nodes of the aorta are saved at fixed time intervals during the deployment. For every node that experiences a non-zero contact force, the force-displacement curve is constructed. A linear fit (based on a linear spring assumption) of the average of all these force-displacement curves is used to calculate the average slope, which corresponds to the characteristic aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} for a certain combination of the input parameters (E_{wall} , E_{TAVI} and t_{wall}).

Theory and boundary conditions for the leaflet model

The high-fidelity simulation of the leaflet model is a solid-shell contact model performed using ANSYS (Mechanical/Explicit solver) on a native aortic leaflet during TAVI placement⁵. A leaflet is constructed using a parameterized multi-patch NURBS geometry presented in D8.8. For high-fidelity leaflet simulations, which are used as an input to the ROM, an average patient leaflet is considered. This average patient leaflet is created by setting the geometric parameters of the multi-patch NURBS leaflet geometry to the average patient data (obtained from CHA, see *D6.2 - Database for anatomy and function based on preclinical and clinical data (CHA, M12)*) listed in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 4.

In this work, the output quantities of interest from the leaflet simulations are the total deformation and reaction forces of the leaflet. The deformation has been successfully modelled with an isotropic linear elastic material⁶ because of its simplicity in modelling and efficiency in computational time. The quantity of interest of a single leaflet during TAVI placement is investigated using the numerical setup shown in Figure 5.

Aortic annulus diameter (D_a)	Leaflet length (L)	Sinus diameter (D_s)
24.07 mm	17.23 mm	31.74 mm

Table 2: Average patient data for the leaflet model

Figure 4: Schematic illustrating the dimensions used for constructing the average patient leaflet.

⁵ High-fidelity leaflet simulations are setup and performed by Deniz Öztunç, Master student, Mechanical Engineering, TUE.

⁶ T.M. Koch, B.D. Reddy, P. Zilla, and T. Franz. Aortic valve leaflet mechanical properties facilitate diastolic valve function. *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering*, 13(2):225–234, 2010. 4

Figure 5: Schematic of the numerical experiments to study the leaflet stiffness. The leaflet (Ω_L) in its closed position is pushed by a semi-cylinder (Ω_B) representing the TAVI device.

Input

The high-fidelity leaflet simulation is used to generate input for the ROM. The aim of this work is to obtain a characteristic stiffness parameter, k_{leaflet} , for the leaflet, that is used in the fast-to-evaluate model described in *D8.8 Fast-to-evaluate TAVI model base on multi-patch NURBS (TUE)*. In this work, the stiffness of the leaflet is computed from force-displacement curves generated by the high-fidelity leaflet model for various Young's moduli (E_{leaflet}) and thicknesses of the leaflet (t_{leaflet}). Average values of these parameters are extracted from the literature⁷. Upper and lower bounds for these two parameters are shown in Table 3 and 32 simulations were performed using a quasi-random sample (generated using Sobol sequences).

Parameter	Lower bound	Upper bound
E_{leaflet} [MPa]	0.5	5.0
t_{leaflet} [mm]	0.2	0.6

Table 3: Input parameters of the high-fidelity leaflet model to generate a quasi-random sample set.

Output

From the high-fidelity simulations, the maximum total deformation (Δ_{Lr}) of the leaflet and the reaction forces (F_{Lr}) on the leaflet are evaluated. The stiffness of the leaflet is estimated based on a linear spring assumption, *i.e.*, $k_{\text{leaflet}} = \frac{F_{Lr}}{\Delta_{Lr}}$. A set of leaflet stiffnesses for the quasi-random input parameters is used as an input to the ROM to estimate the leaflet stiffness, k_{leaflet} . This estimation can be used as an input for the fast-to-evaluate model.

⁷ David Kamensky, Ming-Chen Hsu, Dominik Schillinger, John A. Evans, Ankush Aggarwal, Yuri Bazilevs, Michael S. Sacks, and Thomas J.R. Hughes. An immersogeometric variational framework for fluid–structure interaction: Application to bioprosthetic heart valves. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 284:1005–1053, 2015.

ROM: Adaptive Polynomial Chaos Expansion

Nearly real-time deployment simulations can be performed with the fast-to-evaluate device-deployment model presented in D8.8. However, this model needs input parameters (as will be discussed in the next section) that can be obtained from, for example, high-fidelity simulations. Since these high-fidelity simulations have high computational costs, it would be more efficient to use a ROM to predict the input parameters needed for the fast-to-evaluate deployment model. The theory behind the ROM used in this deliverable is explained in this section.

Theory

A ROM based on Adaptive Polynomial Chaos Expansion theory as presented by Quicken et al.⁸ is used to perform a sensitivity analysis of the three input parameters (E_{wall} , E_{TAVI} and t_{wall}) on the characteristic aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} . The model can also be used to predict k_{wall} for input parameters that are not simulated using the high-fidelity device deployment model. The same is done for the high-fidelity leaflet model, where the input parameters (E_{leaflet} and t_{leaflet}) can be used to predict the characteristic leaflet stiffness k_{leaflet} .

A fast and efficient approach to perform a sensitivity analysis is the *generalized polynomial chaos expansion* (gPCE) method. Here, the model response is expanded into a finite series of polynomials that depend on the so called ‘meta-model’, or model input. However, performing the number of 3D high-fidelity numerical simulations required as input for the gPCE is often too computationally expensive. Therefore, Blatman and Sudret⁹ developed the *adaptive sparse gPCE* (agPCE) approach, which reduces the computational cost compared to gPCE, by only including polynomials that significantly increase the meta-model’s quality.

The computational model can be described using the arbitrary function f , which yields a certain output of interest Y when evaluated for input parameters \mathbf{X} :

$$Y = f(\mathbf{X}). \quad (1)$$

In gPCE, a polynomial expansion is used to obtain an explicit formulation of the function f from Equation (1), by expanding the model output Y into a series of orthogonal polynomials:

$$Y = f(\mathbf{X}) \approx f_{\text{PCE}}(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{\alpha \in A^\infty} c_\alpha \Phi_\alpha(\mathbf{X}), \quad (2)$$

where, Φ_α are the orthogonal polynomials that are functions of \mathbf{X} and c_α are the expansion coefficients. The polynomials Φ_α are constructed by taking products of univariate polynomials φ_{α_i} of order $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{N}_0$ as indicated by the multi-index α :

$$\Phi_\alpha(\mathbf{X}) = \prod_{i=1}^D \varphi_{\alpha_i}(X_i), \quad (3)$$

⁸ Quicken S. et al., 2016, Application of an adaptive polynomial chaos expansion on computationally expensive three-dimensional cardiovascular models for uncertainty quantification and sensitivity analysis, Journal of Biomechanical Engineering.

⁹ Blatman and Sudret, 2010, An adaptive algorithm to build up sparse polynomial chaos expansions for stochastic finite element analysis, Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics.

where D is the number of input parameters. Furthermore, A^∞ is a set that contains all unique multi-indices α and the optimal type of a univariate polynomial to obtain good convergence of the gPCE, which is determined by the probability distribution of the input. The infinite expansion in Equation (2) is truncated to a finite number of terms by including only polynomials with particular properties such as, for example, the total polynomial degree. After this truncation, the expansion coefficients c_α of the meta-model are determined by minimizing the squared difference between the model output and the truncated polynomial chaos expansion using least-squares regression.

To save computational costs the agPCE method is used in this work, where the polynomials included in the meta-model are not chosen *a priori*, but the meta-model is built up adaptively, by only selecting the polynomials that significantly contribute to the ability of the meta-model to describe the original model output. Consequently, fewer high-fidelity simulations are needed to estimate the meta-model's expansion coefficients. It was found that a number of:

$$\frac{(n+p)!}{n!p!} \quad (4)$$

simulations is sufficient to construct the meta-model, where n is the number of input parameters and p is the polynomial degree. More information on the implementation of agPCE and its application to uncertainty quantification and sensitivity analysis of cardiovascular models can be found in Quicken et al.³

Input

The input for the ROM for the device deployment model are characteristic aortic wall stiffnesses k_{wall} obtained from the high-fidelity simulations of 32 simulations with different combinations of the three input parameters (E_{wall} , E_{TAVI} and t_{wall}), leading to a quasi-random sample. The quasi-random sample is created using Sobol sequences. A ROM model is also constructed for the leaflet model. Here the inputs are the characteristic leaflet stiffnesses k_{leaflet} obtained from 32 simulations with different combinations of the two input parameters (E_{leaflet} , t_{leaflet}).

Output

The output of the ROM is the meta-model that can be used to perform a sensitivity analysis and predict the aortic wall stiffness for input parameters for which no high-fidelity simulations are performed. These stiffnesses can subsequently be used to predict TAVI outcomes using the fast-to-evaluate device deployment model.

Fast-to-evaluate device-deployment model

Theory and Boundary Conditions for the fast-to-evaluate device-deployment model

The meta-model developed using the ROM tool can be used to generate input for the fast-to-evaluate device-deployment model as presented in D8.8. With this model, nearly real-time simulations of device deployment can be performed.

In the above-mentioned deliverable, a parametrized multi-patch NURBS was developed for the aorta and the leaflets taking into account the most prominent geometric features (the sinotubular junction, the sinus and the left ventricular outflow track). By doing this, a template geometry can be generated for any desired selection of these features. More details on the multi-patch NURBS approach can be found in D8.8.

A cylindrical stent which expands around a guidewire is used to mimic the implantation procedure in the fast-to-evaluate model. The stent is modeled using a series of expanding catheter segments and the quasi-static mechanical equilibrium of the stent is tracked at each time step during the expansion process during deployment. The model can be considered a semi-explicit model. The contact points are determined at the beginning of each time step and are not updated during the timestep. Therefore, the detection of the contact points can be considered to be explicit. The mechanical equilibrium, however, is treated implicitly, since the response forces are adjusted for the displacement increment computed in the current time step.

Since inertia forces are assumed to be negligible, the forces exerted on the guidewire and stent must be in equilibrium. Two types of forces are considered in the fast-to-evaluate model used in this work: (i) forces exerted at the origin of the guidewire and (ii) forces exerted by contact between the stent segments and the arterial wall. The translational and rotational resistances of the guidewire are modeled using springs with different translational and rotational stiffnesses. To model the contact between the expanding stent and the artery, a fixed set of points on the aortic wall is considered. The distance between these points and the expanding stent is calculated. When this distance is positive, this means that there is contact between the stent and the respective point on the aortic wall and a force is exerted on the stent that is proportional to the aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} and the distance between the point and the stent. When the distance is negative, there is no contact between the point and the stent. After specifying all the forces in the system, the quasi-static equilibrium position of the guidewire can be obtained by solving Newton's law for a quasi-static equilibrium. More information on the implementation of this model can be found in D8.8.

Input

In this work, the characteristic stiffness of the aortic wall k_{wall} and the leaflet k_{leaflet} are needed as input for the fast-to-evaluate model. In future work the maximum force, or oversizing should also be included as an input parameter to train the meta-model. These stiffnesses can be obtained from the meta-models developed using the ROM tool for (i) different combinations of the Young's modulus of the aortic wall, the Young's modulus of the TAVI and the thickness of the aortic wall and (ii) different combinations of the Young's modulus of the leaflet and the thickness of the leaflet, respectively.

Output

The approximate shape of the deployed stent can be obtained as output of the fast-to-evaluate model. From this shape, patient-specific information like the paravalvular leakage (PVL) area for a selection of cross-sectional planes across the height of the aorta geometry can be obtained. See D8.8 for details.

ROM: enhanced fast-to-evaluate model workflow

A detailed representation of the workflow presented in this deliverable is schematically depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the workflow presented in this deliverable.

High-fidelity simulations of the deployment of a CoreValve stent are performed for a quasi-random input set of combinations of material parameters (E_{wall} , E_{TAVI} and t_{wall}), using a virtual aortic geometry of an average patient obtained from the virtual cohort developed in WP7. From these simulations a characteristic aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} and the oversizing of the aorta can be obtained. In this deliverable we focussed only on the characteristic stiffness for the sake of presenting the workflow. The outcome of the high-fidelity simulations is used as input to train the ROM tool presented in Quicken et al.³ to develop a meta-model that can predict the aortic wall stiffness for additional combinations of the input parameters and analyze the sensitivity of this stiffness to the input parameters. The same is done for high-fidelity simulations of the leaflet to obtain a characteristic leaflet stiffness k_{leaflet} . For these simulations two input parameters are used (E_{leaflet} , t_{leaflet}). Finally, the fast-to-evaluate model, developed in D8.8 can be used to perform near real-time deployment simulations, using the characteristic aortic stiffness obtained from the ROM as input. From the fast-

to-evaluate model the deployed shape of the stent can be obtained, which can for example be used to perform a pre-operative risk assessment for PVL. Additionally, the fast-to-evaluate model can provide valuable information on the treatment effects in terms of its global response characteristics. The positioning and orientation of the implanted stent and its dependence on geometry and possible calcifications can be predicted. Even though the fast-to-evaluate model is not suitable for contracting detailed physical information, such as contact stresses, its global response description can help in identifying cases that should be investigated in more detail with high-fidelity models (*e.g.*, cases with PVL areas). Therefore, the approach presented in this deliverable can help to reduce the computational costs for pre-operative risk assessment.

Results

In this section the training data extracted from the high-fidelity models will be discussed. After that, the obtained meta-models from the ROM tool will be presented and used to perform predictions for additional input parameters, not evaluated by the high-fidelity models. These predictions will be validated again by the high-fidelity models. Finally, the fast-to-evaluate tool will be used to perform near real-time simulations using the characteristic stiffnesses obtained from the ROM predictions to show its validity.

High-fidelity device-deployment model

As discussed in the previous section, high-fidelity simulations of the deployment of a CoreValve stent are performed for a quasi-random set of 32 combinations of input parameters (E_{wall} , E_{TAVI} and t_{wall}), using a virtual aortic geometry of an average patient obtained from the virtual cohort developed in WP7.

For every simulation, the radial contact force F_r and radial displacement Δr in every node of the aorta are stored at different time intervals during the deployment. Now, for every node, the radial contact force can be plotted as a function of the radial displacement. To obtain the characteristic aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} , the forces F_r of all nodes are interpolated for 25 fixed radial displacements. For every displacement the average radial force is calculated, and the characteristic aortic wall stiffness is obtained from a linear fit through these points, using a linear spring assumption ($k_{\text{wall}} = \frac{F_r}{\Delta r}$). The average force – displacement curves and their corresponding linear fits are presented in Figure 7 for all 32 simulations.

Figure 7: Average force-displacement curves for a quasi-random set of 32 high-fidelity device deployment simulations and their corresponding linear fits.

To give an idea on the variation of the contact forces in the nodes of the aorta, histograms are created for the simulation from which the minimum and maximum characteristic aortic wall stiffness was obtained at five equally spaced displacement intervals. The results are shown in Figure 8 .

Figure 8: Top: contact forces in the nodes of the aorta after deployment (left: minimal k_{wall} , right: maximal k_{wall}). Bottom: histograms of the radial force for different displacements during the deployment.

From this figure it can be concluded that most of the nodes in the aorta experience a contact force close to the average force used to obtain the characteristic aortic wall stiffness.

High-fidelity leaflet model

This section presents the results obtained using the high-fidelity leaflet model, similar to deployment model presented in the previous section. As discussed in the theory and background of the leaflet model, 32 solid-shell contact simulations are performed on average patient-based leaflets for a quasi-random (Sobol sequence) set of varied Young's moduli ($E_{leaflet}$) and thicknesses of the leaflet ($t_{leaflet}$).

For all 32 simulations, the total leaflet reaction force F_{LR} and displacement Δ_{LR} are extracted at different time intervals. The characteristic leaflet stiffness $k_{leaflet}$ is obtained from a linear fit through the extracted data, *i.e.*, $k_{leaflet} = \frac{F_{LR}}{\Delta_{LR}}$. The total reaction force – displacement curves and their corresponding linear fits are presented in Figure 9 for all 32 simulations. A sample total displacement result is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9: Average force-displacement curves for a quasi-random set of 32 high-fidelity leaflet simulations and their corresponding linear fits.

Figure 10: Total displacement field of a leaflet obtained using a high-fidelity simulation.

Reduced-order model – deployment model

As discussed in the previous section, high-fidelity simulations of the deployment of a CoreValve stent are performed for a quasi-random set of 32 combinations of input parameters (E_{wall} , E_{TAVI} and t_{wall}) to obtain a characteristic aortic wall stiffness k_{wall} . These simulations are used to construct the meta-model using the ROM tool discussed in the Section *ROM: Adaptive Polynomial Chaos Expansion*. This meta-model can now be used to predict values for k_{wall} , for input parameters for which no high-fidelity simulations have been performed. We note that these predictions can only be done for

parameters within the tested range of the high-fidelity model evaluations. The quality of the meta-model can be assessed by the leave-one-out cross-validation coefficient Q^2 . If this value is close to 1, this means that the meta-model can predict the model evaluations accurately. More information on this coefficient can be found in⁷.

Next to performing predictions with the obtained meta-model, this model can also be used to perform a sensitivity analysis of the different input parameters on the variance of the output. To this end, the variance of the output of the model can be composed in fractions, which can be attributed to inputs. The inputs are defined as follows here: 1. E_{wall} , 2. t_{wall} , 3. E_{TAVI} . Different sensitivity parameters can be distinguished and are plotted for the meta-model in Figure 11. In the left figure, the Sobol main index is plotted for all three input parameters. This index measures the effect of varying input parameter X_i , but averaged over variations in other input parameters. The middle figure shows the Sobol total indices of all input parameters. This index measures the contribution to the output variance of input parameter X_i , including the variance caused by its interactions with other input variables. Hence, the difference between the main index and the total index is the amount of interactions that X_i contributes to. The closer these indices are to one, the more important the variable is to the output. The figure in the right shows the interaction effects of the different input parameters. From this figure can be concluded that especially any variation in the thickness of the aortic wall t_{wall} will influence the output k_{wall} .

Figure 11: Sobol indices of the obtained meta-model from the high-fidelity deployment simulations. The inputs are defined as follows: 1. E_{wall} , 2. t_{wall} , 3. E_{TAVI}

To verify whether the meta-model correctly predicts k_{wall} for the chosen input set, the value of k_{wall} obtained from the high-fidelity simulations and the predictions from the meta-model are plotted in Figure 12. From this figure can be concluded that the predictions of the meta-model match very well.

Figure 12: Output of the high-fidelity model (red) for the input parameters used to train the meta-model and the corresponding meta-model predictions (blue).

Finally, the meta-model can be used to obtain predictions of k_{wall} for combinations of input parameters. To this end, ten random combinations of input parameters are chosen. Five of those combinations are chosen close to the boundaries of the input ranges used to construct the meta-model and five combinations are chosen further away from the boundaries to see how accurate the meta-model predictions are within the domain. The chosen combinations and their corresponding high-fidelity output are listed in Table 4. The predictions are again compared to the outcome of high-fidelity simulations. The relative error between the meta-model predictions and the high-fidelity simulations is calculated as follows:

$$\text{relative error} = 100 \cdot \frac{k_{\text{wall,prediction}} - k_{\text{wall,high-fidelity}}}{k_{\text{wall,high-fidelity}}} \quad (5)$$

E_{wall} [MPa]	t_{wall} [mm]	E_{TAVI} [MPa]	$k_{\text{wall,high-fidelity}}$ [N/m]	$k_{\text{wall,prediction}}$ [N/m]
0.52	0.56	84000	6.08	87.71
0.68	3.70	36000	32.34	31.56
4.90	0.68	84000	20.93	-20.51
4.90	0.68	36000	17.20	23.99
0.52	0.56	35500	4.09	13.14
3.80	2.50	55000	86.48	78.18
1.80	3.90	63000	103.21	93.79
2.50	1.80	45000	38.72	39.26

Table 4: Combinations of input parameters used to perform predictions with the constructed meta-model and the corresponding output of the high-fidelity deployment model. The first five combinations are close to the boundaries of the input parameter ranges.

The results of the high-fidelity model evaluations and the corresponding prediction of the meta-model are shown in Figure 13. The left figure shows the results and their predictions for the input parameter combinations close to the boundaries of the input ranges, whereas the right figure shows the results

and their predictions for the input parameter combinations well within the boundaries of the input ranges.

Figure 13: Results of the high-fidelity simulations for the input parameter combinations presented in Table 4 and their corresponding meta-model predictions. Left: input parameter combinations close to the boundaries of the input ranges. Right: input parameter combinations well within the input domain.

The relative error is plotted in Figure 14. From Figure 13 and Figure 14 it can clearly be observed that the meta-model predicts the characteristic aortic wall stiffness reasonably well for input parameter combinations well within the range for which the model was trained, since the relative error is small for these input parameter combinations. Close to the boundaries the predictions get very inaccurate, especially for input parameter combinations that lead to large radial aortic wall displacements.

Figure 14: Relative error of the meta-model prediction for k_{wall} . Inset shows a zoom-in of relative error for the last five input parameter combinations.

From this section it can be concluded that the workflow presented in this deliverable can be used to construct a ROM tool that can predict, within reasonable accuracy, the characteristic aortic wall stiffness needed as input for the fast-to-evaluate device-deployment model. Predictions of the meta-model can be improved by searching for a meta-model with an even higher Q^2 coefficient.

Reduced-order model – leaflet model

The leaflet stiffness k_{leaflet} , evaluated from the linear fit of reaction force – displacement curves of the high-fidelity simulations, are used as training data set to the ROM tool (discussed in the Section *ROM: Adaptive Polynomial Chaos Expansion*). The ROM constructs a meta-model which can predict values for k_{leaflet} for unknown input parameters within the ranges of the trained data set. As mentioned in the previous section, the quality of the meta-model is assessed by the leave-one-out cross-validation coefficient Q^2 .

As a verification of the meta-model, the value of k_{leaflet} predicted from the meta-model is extracted for the provided input parameters and compared with k_{leaflet} from the high-fidelity training set. A comparison is presented in the left panel of Figure 15 and the relative error is presented in the right panel of Figure 15. From this verification, it can be observed that the ROM predictions are very close to the provided training data for the interior points of ranges of the input parameters. However, close to the range boundaries, the predictions become inaccurate.

After verification, the meta-model can be used to predict k_{leaflet} for unknown input parameters within the ranges. Four unknown parameter combinations (not part of the training set) are chosen for the prediction; see Table 5. These input parameters are used to compute k_{leaflet} by performing high-fidelity simulations and are compared with the meta-model predictions (see Figure 16). Similar to the verification, it can be observed that the predictions are accurate for the input parameters in the interior and inaccurate close to the boundary.

Figure 15: Verification of the meta-model at the provided input parameter set. Left: Comparison of the leaflet stiffness k_{leaflet} obtained from the high-fidelity training set and predicted by the meta-model. Right: Relative error of this comparison.

Parameter	Simulation			
	1	2	3	4
E_{leaflet} [MPa]	0.60	3.20	4.20	4.90
t_{leaflet} [mm]	0.31	0.43	0.49	0.57

Table 5: Input parameters of the Young's modulus and thickness of the leaflets for comparison. Note that these parameters are not part of the provided training set.

Figure 16: Verification of the meta-model prediction at unknown parameters. Left: Comparison of the leaflet stiffness $k_{leaflet}$ predicted by the meta-model and computed from the high-fidelity simulations. Right: Relative error of this comparison.

Fast-to-evaluate device-deployment model

In the previous sections we demonstrated that for a certain input parameter set (within the range of the high-fidelity training set) the stiffness of the aortic wall and leaflet can be estimated from the ROM tool. This stiffness can now be used to evaluate the displacement and rotation of the TAVI device using the fast-to-evaluate model. For a stiffness estimated by the ROM tool, the final TAVI deployments are compared between the fast-to-evaluate model and the high-fidelity simulations. First, we will consider a case with a relatively low error. This corresponds to the input set: $E_{wall} = 2.5$ MPa, $t_{wall} = 1.8$ mm, and $E_{TAVI} = 45000$ MPa. For this input set, based on the training data, the ROM tool estimated $k_{wall} = 39.26$ N/m (relative error of 1.3%). The deployment process for the fast-to-evaluate model is shown in Figure 17 for 4 time steps.

Figure 17: TAVI implantation procedure at different time steps (from left top to right bottom). The stent is represented by the yellow cylinder. The reference and transformed guidewire are shown in blue and the aortic wall is shown in red.

Figure 18 shows a direct comparison of the final stent deployment between the fast-to-evaluate model (shown in yellow) and the high-fidelity model (shown by the black stent wireframe). This comparison conveys that the stiffness extracted from ROM tool can be used in fast-to-evaluate model as it represents the position and expansion of the TAVI very similar to a high-fidelity simulation. Evidently, there are also notable differences between the results at the right side. This might relate to difference in the deployment process. However, the displayed result already provides a realistic impression of predicting the TAVI position.

Figure 18: Comparison of the fast-to-evaluate model (yellow) and high-fidelity model (black wireframe).

For a case with a slightly higher relative error, *i.e.*, around 15% (corresponding to input set 9 in Table 4), stiffness of the aortic wall is estimated from the ROM as $k_{\text{wall}} = 97.27$ N/m and computed from the high-fidelity model as $k_{\text{wall}} = 112.10$ N/m. Based on the fast-to-evaluate model, we observed that the TAVI position sensitivity of this error has a negligible effect on the TAVI displacement and rotation (see Table 6).

k_{wall} [N/m]	u [mm]	v [mm]	θ [deg]	ψ [deg]
ROM tool	2.6794448	3.1907894	- 4.294340	4.930689
High-fidelity simulation	2.6794436	3.1907883	- 4.294352	4.930699

Table 6: Comparison of the TAVI displacement and rotation evaluated from the fast-to-evaluate model for the aortic wall stiffness estimated from the ROM tool and high-fidelity simulation (relative error $\sim 15\%$).

Conclusions and recommendations

In the Virtual Research Environment (VRE), envisioned within SIMCor, effect simulations are to be performed on large virtual cohorts. To this end, it is desirable to have a Reduced-Order model (ROM), which can be used to perform fast-to-evaluate numerical simulations at a low cost to show trends, or to decide whether computationally expensive high-fidelity simulations are necessary for a specific patient.

In this deliverable, we presented a workflow on how to use and construct such a ROM. A limited number of high-fidelity simulations is performed to model device deployment and leaflet deformation. The output of these high-fidelity simulations is used to construct a meta-model, using the adaptive sparse generalized Polynomial Chaos Expansion. This meta-model can then be used to predict the desired outcome for input parameters for which no high-fidelity simulations are performed. The predicted outcome of the meta-model can be used as input for a fast-to-evaluate deployment model.

Since the aim of this deliverable was to show the validity of the proposed workflow, we limited the number of input parameters and constructed the meta-model for only a limited number of output parameters. This workflow can be extended to other output parameters for the fast-to-evaluate model, such as the oversizing of the aorta.

The presented results show that the reduced-order meta-model can be used to give reasonably accurate predictions of the chosen output of the high-fidelity simulations. Furthermore, it is shown that the output of the meta-model can be used as input for the fast-to-evaluate deployment model to perform near real-time deployment simulations and that these results are in qualitative agreement with the results of the high-fidelity simulations.

In conclusion, this workflow can be used as a fast tool for pre-operative risk-assessment of the TAVI procedure. To this end, the effect of geometrical features of the aorta, material parameters of the tissue, or initial positioning of the stent on, for example, treatment effects such as paravalvular leakage can be studied. The outcomes of the workflow can be used to decide whether more accurate high-fidelity simulations are needed and can therefore significantly reduce the computation cost for effect simulations on large virtual cohorts.